

Title: ICO: long-term success factors

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INTRODUCTION:

Analysis of 50+ completed ICO client projects, including the following critical components:

- White Paper Development;
- Technological Validation from Architectural and Development perspectives;
- Ecosystem Design and Governance;
- Business Model Tokenization;
- Scalability;
- Blockchain/DLT Platform/Dapp development

AIM:

To share best industry practices and help blockchain startups learn from experiences of other companies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The presentation is an industry analysis based on 50+ critical reviews and advisory projects completed for ICO clients.

CONCLUSIONS:

More than 90% of ICO projects are not adequately prepared to hold their ICO and have very low probability to succeed as companies in the future.

KEYWORDS:

ICO; Initial Coin Offering; Token

BIOGRAPHY:

Mukhtar is a Founder & CEO of BlockSpace Labs Inc., a co-founder of 3 blockchain startups and a blockchain/Dapp development and advisory firm. He is a serial entrepreneur and has an extensive experience in:

- founding and launching several successful hi-tech startups;
- developing corporate governance systems for financial institutions to meet IPO requirements at major stock exchanges;
- investment management, including negotiating economic and financial conditions of 20+ world-class, multi-billion deals in oil&gas and mining industries;
- serving in senior and executive positions at multinational corporations; and
- advising corporations on business strategy and BPM.